

CREATING PRE-, WHILE-, AND POST-LISTENING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The development of effective listening skills is a vital component of language learning. This study explores innovative methodologies and strategies for designing pre-, while-, and post-listening activities to enhance comprehension and engagement in English language classes. By reviewing existing research and incorporating personal experiences in classroom applications, the paper offers practical insights and recommendations for educators.

Keywords: listening activities, pre-listening, while-listening, post-listening, multimedia technology, innovative methodologies.

Introduction

Listening is a cornerstone of language acquisition, yet it remains one of the most challenging skills to teach effectively. Research highlights the importance of structured activities before, during, and after listening tasks to maximize comprehension and retention (Brown, 2006; Brown, 2011). However, traditional approaches often fail to account for the diverse needs of learners or the potential of modern technologies. This paper examines innovative methods, including multimedia and intercultural communication, to create dynamic listening activities that support learner engagement.

Methods

To explore effective listening activities, we reviewed key literature, including works by Brown (2006, 2011) and recent studies on multimedia integration in language teaching (Teshaboyeva, 2023; Musayeva & Mengliyeva, 2022).¹ Additionally, I implemented and tested pre-, while-, and post-listening activities in English language classes using multimedia tools such as audio-visual aids, interactive platforms, and culturally relevant materials. Classroom observations and learner feedback were used to evaluate the effectiveness of these activities.

Results

1. Pre-Listening Activities:

Incorporating multimedia, such as videos or culturally contextual visuals, significantly enhanced students' anticipation and interest. Activities like brainstorming, vocabulary previews, and setting listening goals were effective in activating prior knowledge. For example, showing a short video related to the listening topic encouraged students to predict the content and ask questions, fostering curiosity and readiness.

2. While-Listening Activities:

Tasks like gap-filling, note-taking, and sequencing events kept learners actively engaged during listening. Using interactive apps to pause and discuss specific sections allowed students to focus on critical details and improve their comprehension. These activities also

¹ Musayeva, S. I., & Mengliyeva, S. S. (2022). [Kursantlarning madaniyatlararo rivojlantirish](#).

helped learners develop critical listening strategies, such as distinguishing main ideas from supporting details.

3. Post-Listening Activities:

Reflection and application-based tasks were most impactful. For instance, students were asked to summarize the audio in their own words, discuss the main ideas in groups, and create follow-up questions. These activities deepened their understanding and promoted collaborative learning. Integrating cultural elements in discussions made the content more relatable and meaningful.

4. Challenges and Insights:

Some students initially struggled with using multimedia tools but adapted quickly with guidance.

Personalized activities addressing learners' interests and cultural backgrounds yielded better results.

Discussion

The results demonstrate that combining traditional listening strategies with modern technologies and culturally relevant content leads to a more engaging and effective learning experience. These findings align with Teshaboyeva and Rayimberdiyev's (2023) emphasis on the importance of multimedia in English teaching. Moreover, fostering intercultural competence, as discussed by Ibrohimovna (2019), enriches the listening experience by providing context and relevance.²

Conclusion

Creating structured pre-, while-, and post-listening activities tailored to learners' needs significantly enhances their listening skills. Incorporating multimedia tools and intercultural elements makes the learning process more dynamic and engaging. Future research could explore long-term impacts and the scalability of these methods in diverse educational contexts.

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